

Evaluation of the TEC1-12706 device's performance for the development of a portable Peltier thermoelectric cooler box.

Collins E. Ouserigha, Godwin E. Ogobiri and Ayoro Ebimobowei Lucky

Department of Physics, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

ouserigha.ec@ndu.edu.ng

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the operating performance of a Thermoelectric Cooler (TEC) device by analysing critical relationships, including current, cooling power, coefficient of performance, and thermal management. Experimental data highlight major trade-offs associated with TEC technology. The Coefficient of Performance (COP) has a fast, inverse relationship with current, decreasing from its peak (over 2.1) at low currents (≈ 1.0 A) due to the quadratic dominance of Joule heating in the input power. While cooling power (Q_C) grows with current, the rate of increase slows, indicating that Q_C is approaching its maximum capacity as the linear Peltier effect is progressively negated by nonlinear resistive losses. To achieve the maximum temperature difference ($\Delta T = 40$ °C), a large increase in current flowed through the device, as well as robust hot-side thermal management, as indicated by the rise in T_H corresponding to a lower T_C . This device can be utilised in a portable cooler box for solid state refrigeration due to its high temperature difference and cold side temperature being below zero degrees.

Keywords: Thermoelectric cooler (TEC), cooling power, Peltier effect, coefficient of performance (COP), LiFePO_4 .

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INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for effective, environmentally friendly, and portable cooling solutions in a variety of industries, including medical, food preservation, and leisure, has fuelled extensive research into thermoelectric cooling (TEC) technologies [1, 2]. TEC devices, which operate on the Peltier effect, provide numerous advantages over conventional compressor-based systems, including silent operation (due to their solid-state nature), compact size, the absence of refrigerants (which are harmful to the environment), precise temperature control, and minimal maintenance

requirements [3, 4]. These qualities make them ideal for building portable cooler boxes that can be powered by common low-voltage DC sources, such as those found in cars [5].

The Thermoelectric Cooler (TEC) module is an important component in such cooler boxes, as its performance determines the overall efficiency and cooling capacity of the system [6]. Among the existing thermoelectric modules, the TEC1-12706 device has received extensive attention because of its low cost, dependability, and ease of integration into small-scale cooling systems [7]. However, thermal management within a limited volume, heat dissipation optimisation, and determining the system's actual cooling-down capabilities under real-world conditions continue to be critical areas of research for any specific cooler design [8, 9].

This study conducts an experimental investigation into the performance of the TEC1-12706 module. The module can be powered by a 12 V DC power source and can include optimised heat dissipation mechanisms, such as fin-type heatsinks, to improve thermal management. Previous research shows that the cooling effectiveness of these systems is highly dependent on input voltage, heat sink layout, and ambient conditions [10]. This study aims to assess the actual performance characteristics of a single stage design setup as well as the feasibility of deploying TEC-based cooler boxes in real-world scenarios such as medical transport, outdoor recreation, and off-grid refrigeration by systematically analysing temperature gradients, cooling capacity, and coefficient of performance (COP). The findings will help to expand the practical knowledge basis for creating and optimising small, TEC-based thermal systems. Additionally, they give a cost-effective option to cooling vaccines and beverages in locations without a refrigeration facility [11, 12].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The need for portable cooling solutions has skyrocketed, thanks to outdoor lovers, campers, picnickers, and people who require mobile temperature control for various products. While traditional compressor-based refrigerators are functional, they frequently present issues in terms of size, weight, noise, and power consumption in portable applications. Because of their small size, solid-state operation, and low power consumption, thermoelectric coolers (TECs), particularly those that use the Peltier effect, are an appealing alternative [13, 14]. This article delves into the basic design and performance analysis of the well-known TEC1-12706 gadget. This device could be used in a portable Peltier-based thermoelectric cooler box with a capacity of 10 litres.

The Peltier effect is a thermoelectric phenomenon in which heat is absorbed or emitted when an electric current travels via a junction between two distinct conductors. Peltier modules, or thermoelectric cooler modules, take advantage of this effect. They are made up of several P-type and N-type semiconductor pellets placed between two ceramic plates. When a DC current is supplied, one side of the module gets cold (absorbing heat from the surrounding environment) while the other side becomes hot (dispersed heat). The TEC1-12706 is a popular Peltier module

with a 12V working voltage and a maximum current demand of around 6 amps, allowing for a substantial temperature differential [15, 16, 17].

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research is to measure some performance parameters of the TEC1-12706 Peltier module, determine its suitability for a thermoelectric cooler box, and test its usefulness as a cooling system. The experimental investigation was designed to systematically assess the thermal and electrical performance of the TEC1-12706 Peltier module. The process includes designing and building a single stage cooling system, selecting instruments, and conducting experimental measurements for data collection.

Inkscape, a computer-aided design (CAD) software, was used to draw the system's design configuration, as illustrated in figures 1a and 1b [18]. Figure 1a displays the configuration of fans and aluminium heatsinks connected to the thermoelectric cooler module's cold and hot sides. The cold side of the TEC is connected to an extraction fan and a finned aluminium heatsink from the top, while the hot side (from the bottom) is connected to a finned aluminium heatsink and a cooling fan. Figure 1b depicts a CAD model of the cooler box with the TEC module setup indicated in Figure 1a mounted on two sides (front and back) and a 12 V battery connected.

Figure 1 (a): Connection setup of the Thermoelectric cooler module with the heatsinks and fans.

Figure 1 (b): Model of the thermoelectric cooler box.

Figure 2a illustrates how the TEC1-12706 module was attached. The "cold" side of the module is up, and the "hot" side is down. The hot side of the TEC module creates a large quantity of heat that was efficiently dispersed into the ambient air utilising the heatsink and cooling fan. Failure to do so would result in a significant loss in cooling performance and even damage to the TEC module. To increase the surface area for heat exchange with the air, a huge aluminium heatsink with many fins was connected to the hot side (see figure 2a). An active cooling fan (a 12V DC fan) was then utilised to drive air through the heatsink ends, greatly increasing heat dissipation. The fan size (70 x 70 x 20) and airflow capacity matched the TEC's heat output. The cold side of the TEC module is equipped with a small fan to circulate cold air. Thermal paste was put between the contact surfaces to increase thermal conductivity.

The TEC1-12706 works best at 12V DC. The power source must be capable of supplying at least 6A (preferably a little more for headroom and fan operation), for a total of 72W to 80W. A 12 V rechargeable Lithium Iron Phosphate (LiFePO₄) battery with a capacity of 100 Ah was utilised as the power supply, with current and voltage measured with a digital multimeter. LiFePO₄ batteries are an ideal choice because of their long cycle life, safety, steady voltage output, and lightweight when compared to lead-acid batteries. A 100Ah battery provided enough power to operate the TEC module and fans. The battery is charged externally using a solar panel or an AC-DC adaptor. For temperature measurements, a K-type thermocouple probe was utilised, and a digital multimeter was used to measure current and voltage (see figure 2b). Figure 2c depicts the full module arrangement, which was mounted on a 10-litre cooler box.

Figure 2 (a): The connected TEC module with aluminum heatsink and fans before mounted on the cooler box.

Figure 2 (b): K-type thermocouple (LANDTEK Environmental tester).

Figure 2 (c): A 10-litre cooler box with the TEC module setup installed.

RESULTS

We tested the performance of the TEC1-12706 module to determine its usefulness as a cooling device. The device was set up as shown in Figure 2a, and varied currents were passed through it. Then, current and temperature measurements were collected at a constant supply voltage of 12 V, and other parameters such as input power, heat absorbed (Q_C), and coefficient of performance (COP) were calculated and plotted versus current. Figures 3–7 depict these plots.

Figure 3 depicts the TEC1-12706 thermoelectric cooler's temperature difference (ΔT) vs. input electric current (I). The graph indicates a positive relationship between current and temperature differential, implying that increasing current enhances cooling power, up to the maximum current tested. As the current (I) climbs from 1.0 A to 3.8 A, the temperature differential (ΔT) grows steadily, starting at $\approx 21.0^\circ\text{C}$ and reaching $\approx 37.5^\circ\text{C}$. The convex curve shows a steeper slope, indicating that the rise in ΔT is more noticeable at higher currents within the tested range. The graph shows a rising slope (convex shape) in the range of 1.0 A to 3.8A. This indicates that the ΔT is still predominantly influenced by the linear increase in Peltier cooling. In an ideal case, the ΔT curve would continue to grow until it reaches a maximum (ΔT_{max}) at the optimal current (I_{opt}), and then turn downward [1]. The graph shows no peak, indicating that the optimal current (I_{opt}) for maximum ΔT is more than 3.8 A for this TEC device and experimental setup. If the current is increased further, the quadratic increase in Joule heating will finally surpass the linear increase in Peltier cooling, causing the ΔT to plateau and drop. The result demonstrates that the TEC device performs well within the tested current range, with cooling power continuously increasing as

current increases. The system is currently functioning in the region where the benefits of greater Peltier pumping outweigh the negative consequences of Joule heating, but the point of maximum thermal difference has yet to be achieved.

Figure 3: Temperature difference (ΔT) as a function of input electric current.

The plot in Figure 4 depicts the relationship between the Hot Side Temperature (T_H) and Cold Side Temperature (T_C) of the TEC device. The data indicates a strong negative correlation: when the cold side temperature (T_C) decreases (the device cools more effectively), the hot side temperature (T_H) rises. The hot side temperature (T_H) is determined by the ambient temperature (T_{amb}) as well as the heat sink's ability to dissipate the rejected heat. Further increases in T_H have a direct and detrimental impact on the effectiveness of cooling. This plot clearly shows that the efficiency and cooling capacity are basically restricted by the hot side heat rejection system's efficacy. An ideal cold side temperature ($T_C = -2$ °C) can only be sustained if the hot side heat sink keeps T_H below

a crucial value (in this case, 36 °C). If T_H exceeded around 40 °C (for the existing configuration), the cold side would be unable to sustain a negative temperature.

Figure 4: Relationship between the hot side temperature (T_H) and the cold side temperature (T_C).

Figure 5 depicts the Input Power (in W) against the Input Current (I in A) for the TEC device. The plot reveals a clear, monotonic, and almost linear relationship between input power and current across the measured range (1.0 A to 3.8 A). The data points are extremely close to a straight line that passes near the origin. This indicates that the relationship is roughly linear.

Figure 5: Input power (W) against input current (A) for the TEC 12706 device.

The graph in Figure 6 plots the Heat Absorbed (Q_C) in watts (W), which represents cooling power, against the Input Current (I) in amperes (A) for a Thermoelectric Cooler (TEC) device. The plot demonstrates a monotonic, non-linear growing relationship: as the current grows, so does the cooling power. As the current increases, so does the Q_C , which increases from 25 to 60 W. If the current was increased further (beyond 3.8 A), the curve would eventually plateau at a peak (Q_{max}) and possibly begin to drop. The system is most efficient (highest COP) at low currents (as confirmed by the COP plot in figure 7), but it reaches its maximum cooling power (Q_C) near the end of the working range, when the linear Peltier term is only balanced by non-linear losses.

Figure 6: A plot of the heat absorbed (Q_C) in watts (W) against input current (I) in amperes (A) for the TEC 12706 device.

Figure 7 illustrates a strong negative relationship between the Coefficient of Performance (COP) and the input electric current (I): as the current increases, the cooling process's efficiency decreases dramatically. The COP reaches its peak value (over 2.0) at the lowest current ($I=1.0$ A) and gradually falls, reaching a minimum value of around 1.35 at the maximum current measured ($I=3.8$ A). The low-current region experiences the most rapid loss of efficiency. The shape of this curve is the typical efficiency curve for a TEC, which is described by the competing relationships between heat absorption (Q_C) and electrical power input (P_{in}) in proportion to current. Input power grows quadratically with current. This quick growth is the primary cause of the COP decline. The heat absorbed by the cold side is a mix of linear Peltier cooling and quadratic Joule heating (as described in the Q_C vs I analysis). The net cooling power Q_C increases, but considerably more slowly than P_{in} , and its rate of increase is increasingly slowed by the I^2 Joule heating part in equation (1). Figure 7 shows that our TEC 12706 arrangement is most efficient (COP ~ 2.15) at the lowest current (1.0 A) with negligible quadratic losses. While increasing the current (up to 3.8 A) is necessary to obtain the greatest cooling capacity or temperature differential, it comes at a high

cost in terms of efficiency (COP decreasing to 1.35). However, due to the needed cooling performance of low TC (about 0 oC), an operating current of 3.8 A was chosen for the cooler box.

$$Q_c \approx (\alpha \cdot T_c)I - \left(\frac{1}{2}R\right)I^2 - K \cdot \Delta T \quad (1)$$

Where, α , R and K are respectively the Seebeck Coefficient, electrical resistance, and thermal conductance.

Figure 7: The coefficient of performance (COP) versus current (I) plot for the TEC 12706 device.

CONCLUSION

The performance of the TEC1-12706 device was investigated using a simple design to determine its possible application as a portable Peltier-based thermoelectric cooler box with a 10-liter

capacity. The experimental data demonstrates the basic operational characteristics and intrinsic trade-offs of the Thermoelectric Cooler (TEC) technology. The investigation shows that TEC performance is a complicated balance of cooling power, energy efficiency, and thermal management. The graph of Coefficient of Performance (COP) vs. Current (I) shows a strong inverse relationship: efficiency decreases fast as running current increases (from a peak COP of ≈ 2.15 at 1.0 A to ≈ 1.35 at 3.8 A). This is primarily influenced by the input power (P_{in}) and the quadratic increase in Joule heating ($P_{in} \propto I^2$). The Heat Absorbed (Q_C) vs. Current (I) plot revealed that, while the Peltier effect delivers linear cooling ($\propto I$), the quadratic resistive heating ($\propto I^2$) gradually offsets the net cooling. The Q_C curve flattens out at higher currents (approximately 60 W), indicating the device is nearing its maximum cooling capacity (Q_{max}) under the given ΔT conditions. The graph of Hot Side Temperature (T_H) vs. Cold Side Temperature (T_C) showed a critical dependence on thermal dissipation. To achieve maximum cooling (the lowest T_C , e.g., $\approx -2^\circ\text{C}$), a large increase in current is required, which dramatically rises the heat rejected (Q_H) and therefore the hot side temperature (T_H , up to $\approx 36^\circ\text{C}$). This underscores that the overall ΔT achieved is heavily constrained by the ability of the heat sink to efficiently manage Q_H . Our findings show that the optimal operation of this TEC device necessitates a strategic tradeoff. Low currents provide high efficiency, but at the expense of cooling power and maximum ΔT . Conversely, maximum cooling power is reached at high currents, but at a significant loss of energy efficiency and increased demand on the hot side heat exchanger. Based on the required cooling for vaccines, an operating current of 3.8 A is appropriate to favour high cooling power. Cooler boxes provide an efficient and diverse cooling solution. Its solid-state nature, compact design, and ability to operate from a 12V DC source make it ideal for mobile applications.

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